

Gender and Sexism in *Then She Said it* and *The Missing Face*

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Abstract

There is no other subject matter at present that has gained critical and universal appeal like sexism and gender issues. The reason for this is obvious. In different parts of the world before now, there were laws and edicts barring women from macro and micro schemes and programmes that had direct and indirect impact on them. Women suffered disenfranchisement, occupational segregation and other forms of marginalization. However, this ideological battle has been fought and won by men and women, who recognise the inherent potential in men and women. At present, there is hardly any position in the world, whether social, political or religious that the female has not occupied. The concern of this paper therefore is that whereas the afore stated may be true, some writers, especially those who claim to defend the interest of the female still go all out to bend historical facts in their narratives in such a manner as to show disaffection with the male gender or totally undermine it. This has given rise to some kind of gender chauvinism where, instead of attacking the system that fails to entrench gender equity, the male is at the centre of their assault. This paper anchors on womanism-Africa's version of feminism-which recognizes the complementary roles of men and women in the society to analyze Tess Onwueme's *Then She Said it* and *The Missing Face*. It discovers that, much as Onwueme tries to discourage anti female cultures using drama, she deliberately distorts cultural order and historical facts as a result of gender bigotry.

Keywords: Sexism, Gender, Feminism, Misogyny, Patriarchy.

Resume

À l'heure actuelle, il n'y a aucun autre sujet qui s'est approprié un attrait critique et universel comme le sexisme et les questions sexistes. La raison pour ce phénomène est évidente. Partout dans le monde auparavant, il y avait des lois et des édits interdisant aux femmes de participer à des programmes économiques qui avaient un impact direct et indirect sur elles. Les femmes ont souffert du désenchantement, de la ségrégation professionnelle et d'autres formes de marginalisation. Cependant, cette bataille idéologique a été menée et gagnée par des hommes et des femmes qui reconnaissent le potentiel particulier aux hommes et aux femmes. À l'heure actuelle, il n'existe pratiquement aucune position dans le monde, qu'elle soit sociale, politique ou religieuse, que la femme n'a pas occupée. Notre problématique de cet article est donc que, même si ce qui précède, peut être vrai, certains écrivains, en particulier ceux qui prétendent défendre l'intérêt de la femme, vont tout de même déconstruire les faits historiques dans leurs récits afin de montrer leur désaffection pour le sexe masculin ou totalement pour le négliger. Cela a donné lieu à un genre de chauvinisme sexiste où, au lieu de s'attaquer au système qui ne parvient pas à enraciner l'équité entre les sexes, l'homme est au centre de leur agression. Cet article s'intéresse au womanisme - la version africaine du féminisme - qui reconnaît les rôles complémentaires des hommes et des femmes dans la société pour analyser *Then She Said it* et *The Missing Face* de Tess

Onwueme. Il découvre que, bien qu'Onwueme tente de décourager les cultures antiféministes utilisant le théâtre, elle déforme délibérément l'ordre culturel et les faits historiques en raison du fanatisme sexiste.

Mots-clés : Sexisme, féminisme, misogynie, patriarcat

Introduction

Until recently, in several cultures of the world, women were denied opportunities available to men, not on the basis of ineptitude or any known deficiency or inefficiency, but because they are women. The challenge that trails this ominous assumption becomes more interesting owing to the sympathy it has drawn from writers, especially of the playwriting genre. The demand for gender equality in dramatic literature was first spotted in classical dramas, especially of Aeschylus' *Antigone*, where the eponymous heroine defied the god-like edict of her uncle-king, Creon by burying her brother and damning the consequences. Since then, writers even in Africa have taken a cue in narrating experiences where women challenged existing norms inimical to their cause and engineered revolution to manipulate existing cultural order to their advantage. In *Then She Said It*, which is a dramatic enactment of the militant insurgency in the Niger Delta region of Nigeria for instance, Tess Onwueme tells a story where the women take the lead in the popular call for resource control. And in *The Missing Face*, it is a woman who, against the odds becomes the quintessence of humaneness and repository of cultural mores. By all means, Onwueme is out to reverse gender roles that tend to downplay the abilities and potential of the woman. To that extent, it does not bother her whether her narrative corresponds with historical and cultural facts or slips into anachronism.

Presently, any discourse on gender, especially as it relates to the equal treatment of persons is tagged feminism. Feminism as an ideology now describes every attempt at championing the cause of women even at the expense of cultural values and of socio-cultural norms. Meanwhile, the radicalization of feminism as a phenomenon by the white in the first instance prompted the development of African variants like womanism, motherism, stiwanism and so on, by African female scholars. These feminists' twisting of cultural facts, norms and mores therefore, can agitate the mind to think that either African female writers are yet to come to terms with these concepts, or they are a little confused.

Gender and Sexism: An Overview

Gender is the socially defined capacities and attributes assigned to persons on the basis of their sexual characteristics (Uko:1) Sexism, on the other hand, is the assumption that the members of one sex collectively are superior to those of the other, together with the resultant differentiation practiced against members of the supposed inferior sex ... (Dynes:1). The term is also used to designate conformity with the traditional stereotyping of social roles on the basis of sex. Sexism narrows to the choice of prefixes and suffixes used in certain forms to differentiate between the man and the woman. The table below shows a few examples:

MAN

manager

god

mayor

count

WOMAN

manageress

goddess

mayoress

countess etc

In some climes, the origin of what has come to be misinterpreted as seclusion or marginalization stems from sympathy for, and adoration of the woman's body as delicate, and as such, exempted from hard jobs, and reserved as an object of admiration, of lust and of gratification. Hence, though unofficially, women were exempted from certain strenuous engagements, even as they had their hands full with home chores, childbirth, and child rearing. In the ideal pre-colonial and even post-colonial Igbo culture for instance, though agrarian, women were saddled only with the less strenuous aspects of farming exercise, like weeding and sowing of seeds, whereas the men took care of the more tasking aspects of clearing and tilling. This is before agitations from western industrial societies began to sue for equal rights for men and women in all spheres of life. One pertinent question is whether women are better treated now that they have to combine career with motherly roles than when they were treated like women and respected as such? This does not however ignore certain abuses and inhuman treatments associated with woman-hood in certain cultures, in Africa. The squaring up of women against men has snowballed into the literary world, and has adversely affected narrative ordering and sequencing. At present, it is easy to see a narrative that hitherto had men at the centre of its cause twisted to project feminist ideas. Meanwhile, the ultimate goal of every academic enterprise is the quest for the truth. Truth is so important to academics that most times, it requires an empirical evidence to back up a thesis before it is accepted, and any treatise that cannot be so substantiated is jettisoned as untrue, the plausibility of its narrative notwithstanding. This is without prejudice to certain narratives such as myths and legends, which are often reckoned not to have a definite source but are believed to be true. Even when narratives spring from these mythical or legendary sources, they must be stories that the people can relate with and should be told in such a plausible and convincing manner. When however, writers allow the intoxicating effects of sexism and gender bias to shape their narrative attitude, it is a deliberate attempt to sit truth on the edge of the precipice and credibility is the price.

Gender, Sexism and the Politics of Narration

As earlier observed, in the modern times, as against the initial import of literary creativity which inter alia includes entertainment and education, some female writers conceive literary vocation as gender instrument. This is in their bid to counter the males' purported penmanship onslaught. A popular feminist school led by Mabel Ekwierhoma, suggests that by means of the pen, (which is a pictogram of the male sex organ, penis), the female world has been marginalized. According to this feminist thought, the only way to salvage the situation is for the female to use the same machinery to change the status quo. In her book, *Female Empowerment and Dramatic Creativity in Nigeria* (2002), Ekwierhoma criticized most literatures of contemporary and classical epoch for their misrepresentation of

the female. According to her:

As far back as the classical times, writers like Homer typified the women-hating attitude...his two epics, *The Iliad* and *The Odyssey* respectively treated heroism in battle and home coming, based on survival and death in war. These Homeric works portray women as subordinates, unfaithful and evil. One example is found in the way Helen's infidelity is portrayed as the cause of the Trojan War. Again...the female to Hesiod is frail and greatly incapacitated; hence, he regards the male as supreme (53).

She insists that apart from what Homer and Hesiod said about women, writers like Sophocles portrayed their female characters as weak and unassertive. She cited the example of Jocasta in *Oedipus Rex*, wherein the queen-mother, on discovering herself in the quagmire of incestuous act with her own son, commits suicide by stabbing herself. According to Ekwierhoma even while the problem rages and Jocasta observes the tragic dimension of the circumstances and advises her husband-son to refrain from the quest, he simply ignores her and she did not insist, because the king has spoken. Thus the calamity sweeps across. She concludes that it is this kind of inconspicuous attitude, where the interest of a man defines the destiny of a woman that modern day feminists condemn.

Ekwierhoma's choice of words here seems to align with the tenets of radical feminism—which is considered to be wide in its cause and vile in its content. However, the fact is that the afore-mentioned plays drew their inspiration from the Grecian myth. And the playwrights were not out to twist the facts of history to suit any particular gender, otherwise, they might end up incurring negative reactions from their publics.

Gender and Sexism in *Then She Said It* and *The Missing Face*.

Then She Said It is set in the metaphoric state of Hungaria. Nagging questions and concerns fuel the struggles of rising militant and radicalized women and youths in a dramatized revolutionary struggle for change and challenge to tradition. The relegated women take centre-stage to air their grievances and project their cause to the international community in an effort to destabilize the multinational forces and class interests which have oppressed them for so long (<http://msupress.msu.edu/book>). The play opens with a prologue at the market square, the haven of the disempowered, a scene of wounded women and youths, after a government sponsored raid against them. In annoyance, they decide to tell the world their experience through melodrama (Ekwierhoma 2002:160).

After several futile attempts to draw the attention of the government and the expatriate oil companies to the plight of their host communities, the people decide to take their destinies in their own hands. They engage the government and the oil company in a series of open confrontations and many of them die in the process. This continues until the court intervenes and swings judgment in favour of the community people. The people are afflicted with precarious and demeaning conditions orchestrated by an insensitive regime, represented in the characters of Kainji, the government official, Ethiopie, the people's representative, and, Atlantic- representative of the oil company. Mass murder,

unemployment, raping of single and married women, erosion of arable lands and rivers with components of crude oil without compensation, turn a once peaceful and self-sufficient region into gladiators and serfs in their own land. Consequently, in a bid to survive, the people, especially women take to prostitution, oil bunkering, blasting of oil pipelines, mass protest, placard carrying and demand for resource control. In the people's reasoning, since the coming of the oil companies changed the history of their lives for the worse, the most sensible thing is for the oil companies to go and leave the people to manage their own affairs. So, Resource Control becomes their common slogan.

The Missing Face on the other hand, recounts the story of a young man- Momah, who is in the crisis of self-identity; and a young woman Ida Bee, who cherishes her essence. The play is set in two continental cultural environments-America and Africa. Momah, a young African student, in the USA, goes out selling raffle tickets and walks into the residence of Ida Bee and asks for her patronage. After exchange of pleasantries, they realize they have so many things in common which leads to an uncommon acceptance and accommodation of the visitor. Amorous relationship develops, and the woman gets pregnant for Momah. In his naivety, Momah insists she aborts the pregnancy, and when she refuses, Momah flees, abandoning the woman and her pregnancy and returns to Africa. Meanwhile, Ida Bee has long lost her parents in an unusual circumstance in the USA.

Ida Bee returns to Africa with her Son, Amechi in search of Momah and coincidentally, they meet the villagers at a grotto while performing ritual for Momah. Ida Bee and Amechi are accosted by the villagers, who claim they have desecrated the land by stepping into the sacred ground with their shoes on. All Ida Bee could remember when she is asked about her identity is that she is from Idu in Africa. She, however, is unable to identify the very lineage in Idu to justify her claim. But she recognizes Momah as the father of her son. Momah's mother, Nebe, reacts against the claim of the stranger fearing that it could instigate her son to leave home again. She however softens when unfolding events convince her that the woman is after all her daughter-in-law. In a bid to destroy Ida Bee, Momah lures her into the evil groove and pushes her into it. A ritual is carried out to restore Ida Bee to her senses which she lost immediately she was pushed into the evil groove. A cleansing rite is also performed against the incestuous act between Ida Bee and Momah when it becomes obvious that the two are siblings. It was a herculean task to convince Momah to accept Ida Bee either as a wife or a sister.

In her criticism of the socio-cultural circumstance in the plays, Uko (2004) believes that the current status of the socio-economic life of Nigerian women reveals the diversity of the dynamics of female survival in the Nigerian environment. In her words, "Being a progeny of ages of marginalization and deprivation and a beneficiary of a legacy of brutal sexual discrimination christened by society as tradition, the Nigerian woman exists within confines defined by men, the self-acclaimed representatives of the tradition" (160).

Uko's statement regarding the state of affairs—first in *Then She Said It* and also in *The Missing Face* represents the egocentricity that is associated with a feminist. It is a well known fact that people behave differently. What Momah did cannot represent the attitude of the average responsible male. Secondly, the situation in the Niger Delta which *Then She Said It* reenacts is a generalized situation of mass neglect of men, women, youths, and children, on the part of government of the day. That means that the hardship which the oil

exploration activities and governments' lack of concern to the plight of the people, are without sexist or gender boundaries. That Onwueme chooses to assign men all the vicious roles and projects women as the marginalized and oppressed, is her calculated bid to attract sympathy for the female cause which is the preoccupation of the sexist and gender biased.

In *Then She Said It*, before the play opens, it is the shrieking voices of women that greet the stage, as they fling in as though they managed to escape the holocaust. As their number grows to a sizeable ensemble, now joined by few males, it is still the young women amongst them that realize they have come to the limit of their struggle and it is time for the world to hear their voice. Commenting on the thematic conception of the play, Uko sees the play as a scathing critique of the oppressive, exploitative and corrupt trends in the devastated land of the imaginary Hungeria socio-economic system. According to her:

Hungeria is a metaphor for Nigeria, the renowned African nation with the highest concentration of blacks and one of the leading producers of petroleum in the world. *Then she said It* dramatizes the determination of the exploited, abused and marginalized Niger-Delta women to survive, give voice to their feelings and make alive all that they have known and been put through for decades but which they hitherto could not articulate or react to (2004: 161).

By this statement, Uko seems to paint a picture of the Niger-Delta as a region inhabited alone by women. Or better still a situation of gender war in which men in the region join forces with foreigners to inflict pain on women. My worry here is that the whole idea which Uko tries to project is implicitly and explicitly ingrained in the play by the dramatist. How come a critic like Uko tolls and replicates the ideas warts and all even at the risk of critical reasoning and scholarship? In the first place, the title of the play *Then She Said It*, suggests stridently that the central issues are about women. Again, the play has nine major characters, of which five are women. These women call the shots and hold the ace from the beginning of the play to the end. In short, in Onwueme's characteristic manner, the play is all about women and women alone. The pretentious inclusion of men, who hold one ridiculous role or the other, is to highlight the myriads of ordeals women pass through in the hands of irresponsible men. Hence, the male in their capacities demonstrate austere wickedness, bestiality and heartlessness. It is the women's land and aquatic environment that are destroyed by the oil workers. Those whose sons, daughters, and husbands are killed daily are women. It is the women that cannot get jobs despite their meritorious certificates and qualifications. It is the women that queue in the filling station from morning till night seeking to buy fuel with their money. Men on the other hand, are represented in the characters of the wicked Kainji, the vicious Atlantic, the inhuman Ethiope, the brutal Police, and the ferocious capitalist oil marketer, who would buy and hoard the scarce petroleum product only to resell it at atrocious amounts to the hapless women. And the cruel General, who, untouched by the predicament of the women wants them killed for demanding their rights, is also a man. However, when Onwueme consciously or unconsciously assigns the fuel dispensing role to a female, and she begins to mete out all kinds of ill treatment to

fellow women, she was simply alluding to the fact that people can choose to behave any how, whether as men or women. A parallel of this is also drawn in the characters of Madam Kofo and Omesiete in another of Onwueme's plays, *Shakara Dance Hall Queen*, where Omesiete has to suffer so severely in the hands of a fellow woman, Madam Kofo.

The same wanton sexism and gender bias is replicated in *The Missing Face* with alternating gender characteristics. Men try to protect the interest of the men, while women try to demean men and show-case themselves in the most positive light. These ideas are patently presented in the argument between Odozi and Nebe apparently the sages in the play.

NEBE (disowning her son): I have no son. Never had a son, nor ever will. Our son lost his manhood to a woman whose breast now swells with pride. Hence forth, a woman shall be my song, for I can see through the eye of woman today, the contorted brows of the land bearing the burden of tomorrow.

ODOZI (man): Nebe, a world where women rule is a world of dream...of fancied colours in the rainbow, wearing a thousand shades of uli seed that are marked from the rays of feeling sun. Deny that the sun's phallus does not penetrate the inner depths of your being! Though you may wince and groan below, man, always will be above woman...

NEBE: Enough of that now. For years, the hearts of women have dangled in the pendulous swing for ways of men. A daughter now takes the paddle that stirs the canoe to the shore... The sheep which boasts of the ram as its only child is childless (41).

This dialogue nonetheless is Onwume's method of countering men's patriarchal hegemony. Odozi represents the egoistic male, while Nebe embodies the wise, affectionate, sensible, homely and responsible but intuitive female. In her last line, she paints the picture of the male, represented in the character of Momah, as a ram or he-goat, which goes about producing for the public but has none for him, and ends up breaking the heart of the mother. "The sheep which boasts of the ram as its only child is childless". Apart from the labour loss of this proverbial ram, its major undoing is its irresponsibility to its owner. Momah, like the ram, goes to America, finds a sheep (Ida Bee), impregnates her, leaves her with his own seed and never bothers to ask. He remains unmarried all these years (about seventeen years) and probably goes about sleeping with the village maidens and widows. What a ram! In contrast, Ida Bee bears the child, nurses him to maturity and brings him home to his people. Another demonstration of female level-headedness is shown in the character of Nebe against Odozi. Initially, when Ida Bee appears with her son, Amechi and claims that Momah is the father of her son, Nebe challenges her and tries to protect her son's interest. But when she is convinced that Amechi and his mother are actually members of her family, she starts demonstrating endearing concerns over them, against the hateful disposition of Momah and the indifference of Odozi.

Unlike Momah, Ida Bee epitomizes benevolence, culture consciousness and love. Having lived in Milwaukee, America, for several years, she still does not lose sight of her ancestral roots. She preserves the second half of the Ikenga (wooden fetish), which her father gave to her during her birthday. She values African culture much more than that of the white. When Momah introduces himself as Jack, this culture conscious woman demands:

IDA BEE: Most African names have meaning. What is the meaning of Jack?

MOMAH: Hmn...well, I don't know. Don't know really...em...it's just a name. A name has no meaning. What should I care about the meaning of a name, anyway?

IDA BEE: A lot, I suppose. What is your African name?

MOMAH: Does it really matter?

IDA BEE: It matters! It does! To me... to us...who are here... it has to do with the true identity...A man who knows the meaning of his name answers to the ancestral rhythm and knows where he is going (26-27).

The playwright's portrayal of the male as a confused and irresponsible genius is further stressed by the voice in the grotto:

VOICE (Angrily again): If you were your father's son, you would dig out his spirit. If you were a true son, of the great father, you would walk bold. You son of Africa! Do you know yourself? (49).

There seems to be a calculated attempt at smearing the character of the male by portraying him in various derogatory forms and language. He is the one who does not know himself, and one who is associated with myriads of wicked and senseless acts. In short, the height of character assassination displayed in these plays can only come from a feminist. This ideological archetype may not immediately be located within any Igbo cultural matrix, where it is purportedly situated. However, in keeping with our willingness to suspend disbelief, we agree with the playwright that all the men in her plays are irrational and thoughtless in their decisions. But here again, cultural history and reality as we know it, has been distorted on account of the writer's sexist attitude and gender bias. There can never be any culture in the world where the male in a community are all senseless and uncoordinated.

Conclusion

Onwueme aims at using the instrumentality of drama to raise the consciousness of the female to be relevant in a professed world of male hegemony. Her attempt is to make women realize that they can only take their rightful place by struggling for it. She is so convinced that women have all it takes to assume any position in the world. This thought agrees with the tenets of womanism. As a theory, womanism inter alia believes that if the fight against obnoxious cultural practices and other limiting socio-political and religious factors against women must be won, women ought to see the male counterparts as partners rather than enemies. From history, the victory recorded so far in this fight is through the collective efforts of men and women. The method of fighting should be that of

concretization, and not of confrontation or by abdication of family and cultural responsibilities. Again, victory can never come by challenging ethical values and social norms. Any such aberrant situation can only place family life and sustainability on the edge of the precipice, and create fear over the ability of the female to still be mothers and friends of the family. There should not, for instance, be any reason why divorce cases should be on the rise in Africa just because women want to take their rightful positions in society. This negates the revered and age long concept of 'di bu ndidi' (marriage is patience) which has sustained marriage and family life in Africa. 'Women should rather stoop to conquer'. The playwright and other social reformers should teach this, and be very careful in their choice of words and actions in their narratives, so as to maintain moderation in this quest for female emancipation. This has become very important in view of the possibility of inciting African women to veer into excesses for which their western counterparts are currently known.

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